

filtered, crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether (b. p. 60–80°) mixture and characterised as 2 (Table 1).

Ir spectra (nujol) were recorded on a Carl-Zeiss Specord 75 spectrophotometer.

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A Simple Method of Oximation. Transformation of Steroidal Nitroolefins to Ketoximes

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METHODS are reported for the transformation of nitroolefins into ketoximes^{1,2}. Some of these methods are rather drastic. This communication describes a simple method using methylamine, zinc dust for the conversion of 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1), its 3 β -chloro (2) and 3 β -acetoxy analogues (3) into 5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (4), 3 β -chloro (5) and 3 β -acetoxy (6) ketoximes in 78–85% yields.

Experimental

To a well stirred solution of 6-nitrocholest-5-ene (1) dissolved in ether-methanol (50 ml; 1:1) containing methylamine (15.0 ml, 40% in H₂O), zinc dust (3.0 g) was added at room temperature. The change of colour in ~1 h indicated the completion of the reaction and was also monitored by tlc. The reaction mixture was filtered into a separating funnel containing water and washed with water several times. The ethereal solution was dried over sodium sulphate (anhydrous) and evaporated. The semi-solid thus obtained was re-crystallised to give 5 α -cholestan-6-one oxime (4) (780 mg, 78%), m.p. 197° (lit.⁶, 197–98°). Under similar reaction conditions, nitroolefins 2 and 3 provided ketoximes 5 (800 mg, 80%), m.p. 173° (lit.⁶, 175°) and 6 (850 mg, 85%), m.p. 200° (lit.⁷, 201°).

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Condensed 1,8-Naphthyridines. Part-VII.

Synthesis of 6H-Indeno[1,2-b][1,8]-naphthyridin-6-one

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IN continuation of our studies on the synthesis of 2,3 fused¹⁻⁴ and substituted⁵⁻⁷ 1,8-naphthyridines, we report in this note the synthesis of the hitherto unreported 6H-indeno[1,2-b][1,8]naphthyridin-6-one.

The starting compound 2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine-3-carboxylic acid (I) was obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis of 3-cyano-2-phenyl-1,8-naphthyridine, which in turn obtained by the condensation